

ROLE OF SUBHASHITAS IN CREATING A MODEL SOCIETY

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Abstract

Objective

Subhashitas are simple short epigrammatic poetic verses which convey treasured messages through interesting examples. Our rich Sanskrit heritage has subhashitas relevant to all arenas of life. In our traditional Indian education system Subhashitas are mainly taught to the children at very early age, especially choosing the ones related to righteousness, truthfulness, knowledge, education, service, friendship, courage and patriotism. These subhashitas quote elegant practical examples in them. They guide the children in distinguishing between the good and the bad, help them in deciding “what to do” and “what not to do” by projecting the virtues of the good and showcasing the ill effects of the bad. When the children grow up memorizing and listening to these subhashitas, they imbibe the morale values which the subhashita portrays and become good citizen of our nation. “Today’s children are tomorrow’s citizen”, it is our citizen who create a model society, and they do it based on their personality, education, thinking abilities and the values inherent in them. The main object of this research is to demonstrate that subhashitas act as one of the key ingredients in creating a model society.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- Methodology followed in this research is Qualitative analysis and this work is conceptualized based on various reference materials which are collections of subhashitas, websites which has subhashitas on multiple subjects and research paper related to this subject. Vedas, Upanishads, Puranas, Bhagavad Gita, Mahabharatha and Ramayana, works of our great Sanskrit scholars like Kalidasa, Bartrhari, Bana, Bharavi and Bhavabhuti etc. are main sources of subhashitas. Panchatantra and Hitopadesha are collection of Sanskrit fables which use subhashitas to express the inherent wisdom in the stories.

Findings – Subhashitas are immortal sayings which are memorized and transmitted by word of mouth. Ethical advice and guidance becomes preachy and doesn't appeal to human mind when it is in normal textual form, rather if the same advice is in simple poetic form of subhashita it appeals better. Subhashitas are like “sugar coated bitter medicine”. If children grow up listening to subhashitas they grow up understanding the hidden values which the Subhashitas convey, these moral values make them the responsible citizens who can contribute something great to the society.

Limitations – There are multiple ways through which subhashitas contribute in creating a model society, even though this research describes various aspects of the same it mainly describes the impact of subhashitas on children who grow up listening to them since their childhood.

Practical implications – This paper can inspire people in teaching subhashitas to their children at very young age so that children grow up understanding the moral values in them and become the good citizen.

Keywords – Subhashitas, moral values, children, education system.

1. Introduction

The word “Subhashitam” is defined as “Sushtu Bhashitam”[1]. It means “Eloquent saying”. In Sanskrit the words “Sukti”, “Sadukti”, “Neeti” etc. are used as synonyms of the word “Subhashitam.” Subhashitas are good sayings which describe the experiences of people and portray the moral values with brilliant examples in an appealing poetic manner. They can be in the form of both prose or poetry but we mainly see them in the form of poetry. In Sanskrit literature there are thousands of works related to vedas, puranas, itihasas, kavyas etc. which have many Subhashitas in them. There are a few literary works which explicitly has only Subhashitas. For example Bartrhari's Shatakatravayam .i.e. “Shringara Shatakam, Neeti Shatakam and Vyragya Shatakam”. It has many sub divisions such as Moorka Paddati, Vidvat Paddati, Sajjana Paddati etc.[3]

There are many scholars who have gathered subhashitas from all the sources, classified them based on the subjects and explained them in their Collections. Examples of this category of works are Sridharadasa's “Sadukti Karnamrutha”, Vallabhadeva's “Sukti Muktavali”, Harikavi's “Haaravali” etc. There are many literary works which are translations of Sanskrit Subhashitas into English, Kannada and Hindi languages.

We can see beautiful subhashitas in hundreds of poems written by Bharavi, Kalidasa, Magha etc. Ramayana and Mahabharatha are treasure of Subhashitas. Our culture and oral tradition emphasizes on memorization of Subhashitas. Classic examples in Subhashitas help us in imbibing the hidden morale in our lives. Subhashitas guide us when we are in distress, brings in a vision in our minds and motivates us to achieve our goals.

2. Subhashitas describing Subhashitas

The speciality of Sanskrit literature is, there are many Subhashitas which describes the glory of Subhashitas. A few of them are as follows.

“Bhasasu mukya, madhura, divya, Geervana Bharathi |

Tatrapa kavyam madhuram, tasmadapi Subhashitam||”

- Subhashita Ratna Bhandagara

This is a very famous Subhashita from Subhashita Ratna Bhandagara. It states that, among all the languages ‘Geervana Bharathi’ i.e. Sanskrit is the sweetest, important and devine language. In Sanskrit language ‘poetry’ is the sweetest and in poetry ‘Subhashitam’ is the sweetest.

“Draksha mlaanamukhee jaata, Sharkara chaasmatam gata|

Subhashita rasasyagre sudha bheeta divam gata||”

- Subhashita Manjari

Here the poet humorously glorifies the greatness of Subhashitas. According to him all sweet substances fail to become great in presence of subhashitas. He describes that sweet grapes withered, sugar turned into stone and even nectar was scared and ran up to heaven in the presence of nectarian subhashita.

“Pritivyam threeni ratnani, Jalam, Annam, Subhashitam|

Mudhaihi pashana khandeshu, rathna sangnya vidheeyate||”

- Subhashita Manjari 1.5

Here the poet says that there are three jewels on this earth namely water, food and good sayings. Only fools call the stone pieces as gems.

“Samsara Visha vrukshasya, dve phale hyamrutopame|

Subhashita rasaasvadaha, Sangathihi sujanihi saha||”

- Subhashita Manjari 1.8

Here the poet compares life to the poisonous tree. According to him in the poisonous tree of life there are two nectarian fruits, they are tasty noble saying and the company of noble people.

From all the above subhashitas it is evident that verse form is easier way of remembering text and can be sung in tunes. They contain words framed in a rhythmic manner that are pleasing to

the ear. Subhashitas are very close to everyone's lives and are evolved from experiences of the great. These subhashitas protect people in difficulty, if people lead their life as per the sayings in subhashitas their life blooms like flower. People have to pass through lot of hurdles in achieving their goal and attaining happiness which is momentary. The noble sayings guide people to lead a peaceful life and company of good friends makes sure that our life is full of harmony and happiness.

3. Some of the Popular Subhashitas

“Vidhya mitram pravaseshu, Bharya mitram gruheshu cha||

Vyaditasyowshadham mitram, dharmo mitram mrutasya cha||”

Knowledge is friend in the journey, wife is the friend at home, medicine is friend in illness and dharma is the friend after death.

“Yatha dhenu sahasreshu, vatso vindati mataram|

Tatha purvakrutam karmam kartaramanugacchathi||”

Like how a Calf recognises its mother among the herd of thousands of cows; the same way, karma of previous birth (good and bad deeds) goes with the doer.

“Shoko nashayathe dhairyam, shoko nashayathe shrutam|

Shoko nashayathe sarvam, Nasti shoko samo ripuhu||”

This is a subhashita from Ramayana. Grief destroys one's courage. It destroys one's learning. It destroys one's everything. There is no enemy greater than grief. These are the words of Kausalya. She had spoken harsh words to Dasharatha for sending Rama to the forests. She repents and says that she spoke thus because of her intense grief on Rama being sent to the forests.

“Satyameveshwaro loke, satye dharmaha samashrithaha||”

Truth controls this world and dharma is rooted in truth. These are words of Rama to Maharshi Jabali who advises him to ignore his father's wishes and go back to Ayodhya. The Maharshi speaks like a nastika and makes disparaging remarks about dharma, truth, good conduct, character etc. Rama, however, reiterates the values of truth, dharma and character in a man's life.

4. Indian Traditional Education System

In vedic era, due to the absence of written material, schools in India had an effective system of transferring knowledge to successive generations in the form of hymns. Educations involved three basic processes. They are:

- “Shravana”- Acquiring knowledge of Shrutis by listening.
- “Manana”- Analyzing what they heard, assimilating the lessons taught by their teacher and making their own inferences.
- “Nidhidhasana”- comprehension of truth and apply/use it into real life.

Since our Shrutis were in poetic form and were full of good sayings, it had a great impact in the mind of young students. They grew up listening to these Shrutis, analyzing them and implementing them in their lives.

There was no caste bar for education. Our great sage Vashishtha was the son of Urvashi (a Gandharva women), Vishwamitra the maker of Gayatri mantra was a Kshatriya, Vyasa who has authored Mahabharata was a son of fish woman. Valmiki who was a hunter has authored Ramayana. This shows that Indian society respected the highly educated achievers from humblest origins. The works of these great men are the treasure of Subhashitas.

In Ancient India even women were given equal right to education. We had great women seers like Gargi, Mytreya etc. who were participating in educational debates of Assemblies or “Parishads”. India had great universities like Takshashila, Nalanda etc. which were considered to be the best universities of the times in Indian subcontinent. People from other countries like China, Japan Korea etc. chose to be students of these universities here for higher studies.

India even today focuses on value based primary education. It is always believed that the moral values which children learn at early age acts as a strong foundation for building their personality. Subhashitas, good sayings, patriotic songs and moral stories are taught to the children since the beginning of their education career. The main agenda behind this is to make sure that children grow up into responsible citizen listening to these subhashitas, moral stories, patriotic songs etc. which will definitely have an impact on their personality so that, they can provide their best contributions to the society. This is one of the main reasons why primary education in India is even today globally appreciated.

5. Some interesting stories

• Story of Two Parrots

We have an interesting story of two speaking parrots in “Panchatantra” which demonstrates that “The way we speak depends on how we are brought up”. There were two parrots in the jungle which were playing together on trees. Unfortunately, one parrot was caught by the hunter and the other flew away to a hermitage. One parrot was brought up at hunter’s hut and another in hermitage where some holy men lived. Both these parrots grew up listening and learning what the people around speak. Once a traveller passed by the hunter’s hut. He sat

below a tree to take some rest. Parrot sitting on the tree started shouting “Fool, why have you come here? I will cut your throat.” Surprised by this action of parrot the traveller immediately left the place and started walking. After some time he reached the hermitage and sat below a tree. For his surprise a parrot sitting on the tree above started speaking. “Welcome, traveller. Welcome to this hermitage. We have a lot of good fruits in this forest. Eat whatever you like. The holy men will treat you well.” Surprised by this action, the traveller again spoke with the parrot. “I met a young parrot near a hunter’s hut. It spoke badly. I left the place immediately. Now I have met you. You speak so well. Your words are kind and gentle. Both you and the other birds are parrots. Then why is this difference in your language?” The parrot in the hermitage guessed that the other parrot was none other than its brother. The hermitage parrot said, “Traveller, the other parrot is my brother. But we have lived in two different places. My brother has learnt the hunter’s language. But I have learnt the language of holy people. It is the company that shapes your words and deeds.” This shows that “Good company helps you learn good things. Bad company makes you learn bad things.”

This is not just something which we understand by listening to stories like this, but this is something which we observe everywhere. Language of three year kids from rural area is entirely different the language of the kid brought up in cities. It is not just the region which matters here, but the environment in which kids grow matters a lot. Kids learn speaking by listening to the people around. They develop their vocabulary by listening to what others speak. They learn all the good and bad words spoken by people around and use it in the sentences they frame. Linguistics research says that children at the age of five years have the capability of learning five languages. Everything depends on the environment in which they grow. In many Indian families we can see small kids fluently chanting many shlokas. We most of the times see small kids reciting Rhymes and Moral stories. Patriotic songs are taught to children in school at this age. All these are done to build moral values in the children’s mind. When the children grow up with these thoughts they tend to become good citizen for our nation.

- **Stories behind Bharavi’s famous Subhashita**

An interesting Subhashita from Bharavi’s Kiratarjuneeyam is as follows.

“Sahasavidadhita na kriyam|

Avivekahaparamapadam padam||

Vrinatehi Vimrushya karinam|

Gunalubdaha svayameva sampadaha||”[2]

One should not act in hurry, tasks done without foresight lead to disasters. Wealth itself goes in search of people who think and act and have good qualities.

In Bharavi's Kiratarjuniya, this is a subhashita which Dharmaraja says to impatient Bhima who wants to take revenge on Kauravas. There are many interesting stories about this subhashita.

Bharavi demonstrated great capacities of a writer even from his youth. While everyone around was praised him, his dad would hide his own happiness and say, "He is still a kid, what ability he might have? What will he know of the mystery of Poetry?" Maddened Bharavi with wicked thinking surpassing him plans to kill his dad. As he plans to kill his dad, he hears his mom asking the same question to his dad. His dad tells his wife "Do you think I don't have the idea about our child's capacities? There is no doubt about his capabilities. Despite the fact that others applaud him, we should not do as such before him if we wish his prosperity". Listening to this Bharavi felt ashamed and prostrated before his dad and requested pardoning and a punishment. His dad asked him to stay at in laws house for six months as punishment. Bharavi thought how could this be a punishment and went to in laws house along with his wife.

He received royal treatment for a few days and later on when they found that he was not returning back, the royal treatment turned into a lot of disrespect. This is when he realized why his father gave this punishment. One day, his wife was unable to bare these insults and was crying. Bharavi wrote the above subhashita and asked her to sell this subhashita for money. A merchant bought the same for hundred gold coins and this sufficed till end of six months at her father's house.

Another story says that, Bharavi worrying about poverty wrote this subhashita on a lotus leaf through his nail sitting on the bank of a pond. A King passing by saw and liked the subhashita, etched the subhashita in gold frame and hung it in his bed room. One day when a king came back home after a long time, saw a stranger sleeping next to his wife on bed. Angry king suddenly took his sword and wanted to kill both his wife and the stranger. But suddenly he saw the Subhashita hung on the wall. He calmed down and woke up his wife; his wife was very delighted to explain him that the stranger was none other than their son who was lost long back. The king realized that this subhashita saved the lives of his queen and son, he located Bharavi and honoured him.

The greatest strength of subhashita is to provide comfort in difficult times. They provide answers to our difficult questions. They take us in right track and prevent us from doing wrong deeds.

6. Creating an ideal society

“Om Asato maa sad-gamaya,

tamaso maa jyotir-ga-maya,

mrtyor-maa amrutam gamaya.

Om Shaantih Shaantih Shaantihi.”

- Brihadaranyaka Upanishad 1.3.28 [5]

This is an interesting quotation from Brihadaranyaka Upanishad. This is recited as a prayer requesting lord to take us from unreal to real world, lead us from darkness to light, lead us from death to immortality and may there be peace everywhere.

When we recite such slokas it creates a sense of ‘Jagrithi’ in our minds and motivates us to perform good deeds. The key values which subhashita touch upon are honesty, justice, righteousness, proper use of time, tolerance etc.

Taittiriya Upanishad says “Satyam vadha, Dharmam chara, Svadhyayam ma pramadaha” which means “Speak the truth, practice Dharma and do not neglect the study of Vedas”. Subhashitas even warn us not to just recite the quotations from sacred texts, but also understand the hidden treasure in them and bring it into action in appropriate circumstances.

An ideal society is a place where people have the same right and freedom regardless of their ethnicities, languages they speak and religion they practice. In an ideal society each and every individual should be respected, common goal of everyone should be to create a better world. This is nothing but the concept of “Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam” which our Maha Upanishad portrays.

To achieve all this proper education is required. Only when people are educated they can contribute something better to the society. Educated individuals can create the model society. Here education merely doesn’t mean the degrees which the people hold, but it is mainly related to the moral values which the education brings in an individual. There are many subhashitas which explains the glory of knowledge.

“Vidhya dadati vinayam, vinayat yati patratam|

Patratvad dhanam apnoti, dhanat dharmam, tatah sukham||”

This means knowledge gives humanity, from humanity one attains good character, an individual with good character earns wealth, which can be used for good deeds and to attain happiness.

“Nasti vidhya samam chakshuhu, nasti satya samam tapaha|

Nasti ragha samam dhukham, nasti tyaga samam sukham||”

There is no sight such as knowledge. By knowledge one can see what cannot be seen through a naked eye. Knowledge gives the vision to see beyond some obvious things. There is no ‘tapah’ equivalent to truth. Here we can call ‘hard work’ as ‘tapah’. One has to do lots of hard work to be on the side of truth. There is no sorrow such as desire. Desire of a person brings sorrow to

him. There is no happiness such as sacrifice. Tyaga or sacrifice brings more happiness to the person. Whenever you sacrifice some thing for your loved ones the happiness you get is not something which can be described, but can only be experienced.

We can create an ideal society only when we learn the secrets of life. Subhashitas guide us how to prosper in this world.

“Shad dhoshah purusheneha, haatavya bhutimicchati|

Nidra, tandra, bhayam, krodaha, alasyam, dheergasutratha||”

- Panchatantram [4]

One who wishes to prosper in this world should keep back the following six faults. Too much sleep, lethargy, fear, anger, laziness and miserliness. Only when we come out of these six faults we can achieve something in life. As per Swami Vivekananda’s sayings we should “Arise, Awake and Stop not till the goal is reached”.

7. Conclusion

Subhashitas touch upon values such as fairness, talent, tolerance, patriotism and sense of responsibility. It helps us to determine what ones duties should be. Subhashitas impart ‘Samskaratmaka’ knowledge. The key focus of many subhashitas is dharma. It tests our moral values and makes us better human beings in the process. Subhashitas teach us how to overcome the difficulties in life. We can understand the ethical doctrine of Karma through subhashitas which helps us in achieving Purusharthas of life. It stresses on the point that people gain their positions because of their own attributes and heroic actions. It helps us to understand the fact that, minds of extraordinary people are stronger than thunderbolt and yet softer than flower. Subhashitas describe the qualities which every individual should have such as purity, generosity, chivalry, equally poised in happiness and distress, politeness, affection, and truthfulness. It provides everything which is required to create a model society. When children grow up listening to these subhashitas they understand everything which is required for creating a model society. Today’s children are tomorrow’s citizen. It is the responsibility of every citizen to create a better society. Subhashitas provide all the ingredients required for recipe of creating a model society. It depends on how individuals makes use of these ingredients and create a better society which intern creates a better world.

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